

BamSurgeon simulation (WES)

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Allele fraction type

- Reference truth (black circle)
- Real variant (red circle)
- Simulated variant (green circle)

Batch

- A 1
- B 2
- C 3
- D 4
- E 5
- F 6

Allele fraction (AF)

log10(depth)

Mutation

.CNT

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